

**COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK SOMATIC IDIOMS AND
USING INNOVATIVE PLATFORM “QUIZZIZ” AS A SYSTEM OF EXERCISE IN
TEACHING SOMATIC IDIOMS TO UNIVERSITY STUDENTS.**

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Abstract. Like many other linguistic units, phraseological units containing body parts in English have been applied to various researches. However, little research has been done to explore linguacultural specificity of somatic idioms in the English and Uzbek languages. This paper, based on comparative analysis of somatic idioms in reflecting the national and cultural identity of the nation. In addition, the novelty of this research is that it not only analyzes the previously used exercise system, but also sheds light on the new technology used in this direction, the “QUIZZIZ” platform and its exercise system.

Keywords: comparative analysis, full compliance, partial-matching, the lack of correspondences, the system of exercises, “QUIZZIZ”.

Аннотация. Как и многие другие языковые единицы, фразеологизмы, содержащие части тела в английском языке, нашли применение в различных исследованиях. Однако исследований по изучению лингвокультурной специфики соматических идиом в английском и узбекском языках проведено мало. Данная статья основана на сравнительном анализе соматических фразеологизмов, отражающих национально-культурную самобытность нации. Кроме того, новизна данного исследования заключается в том, что оно не только анализирует ранее использовавшуюся систему упражнений, но и проливает свет на новую технологию, используемую в этом направлении, платформу «QUIZZIZ» и ее систему упражнений.

Ключевые слова: сравнительный анализ, полное соответствие, частичное совпадение, отсутствие соответствий, система упражнений, «QUIZZIZ».

Annotatsiya. Boshqa ko‘plab lingvistik birliklar singari ingliz tilidagi tana qismlarini o‘z ichiga olgan frazeologik birliklar ham turli tadqiqotlarda qo‘llanilgan. Biroq ingliz va o‘zbek tillaridagi somatik idiomalarning lingvomadaniy o‘ziga xosligini o‘rganish bo‘yicha kam tadqiqot olib borilgan. Ushbu maqola millatning milliy va madaniy o‘ziga xosligini aks ettirishda somatik idiomalarning qiyosiy tahliliga asoslangan. Qo‘shimcha tarzda bu izlanishning yangiligi shundan iboratki, u oldin qo‘llanilgan mashqlar tizimini tahlil qilibgina qolmasdan bu yo‘nalishda qo‘llanilgan yangi texnologiya “QUIZZIZ” dasturi va mashqlar tizimini yoritib beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: qiyosiy tahlil, to‘liq muvofiqlik, qisman moslik, muqobil variantlarning mavjud emasligi, mashqlar tizimi, “QUIZZIZ”.

Introduction

In order to speak a foreign language as a native speaker, we need to know, be able to understand and use set expressions or idioms. English, in terms of the presence in its extensive system of idiomatic expressions, is perhaps one of the richest. Idioms occupy a huge layer in its structure. They can be heard in daily conversations, friendly conversations, discussions, business meetings. They can also be found in fiction, newspapers, magazines, television programs. Idioms give the language a bright color, make it more lively, emotional and informal. By definition, an idiom is a phrase consisting of two or more words, the meaning of which is not determined by the

meaning of its constituent words. Obviously, an English idiom is a turn of speech that is not transmitted verbatim into Uzbek.

In general, the history of knowledge of the science of phraseology can be divided into three chronological periods:

First period: it includes the period from the middle of the 19th century to the 30s of the 20th century. The establishment of phraseological knowledge in this period is connected with the scientific activities of M.V. Lomonosov, V.I. Dal, A.A. Potebnya, F.F. Fortunatov, F.I. Buslaev, Sh. Bally, A.A. Shakhmatov. It should be noted that in the first period, phraseology served more as an object of lexicography, that is, of practical lexicology.

Second period: it developed in connection with the scientific works of scientists such as Ye.D.Polivanov, V.V.Vinogradov, S.I.Abakumov, G.K.Danilov, G.O.Vinokur, V.N.Derjavin, A.I.Efimov, A.Ya.Rozhansky, I.E.Anichkov and includes the 30s of the 20th century. This period can also be called the period of formation of an independent linguistic field of phraseology.

The third period starts from the 60s of the 20th century and continues until now. This period is characterized by the use of new methods in phraseological research, the rapid development of phraseological theory and the development of many phraseologists.

In the past forty years, in the Commonwealth of Nations, Azerbaijani (K. Yu. Aliyev, G. A. Bayramov, A. Gurbanov, N. R. Ragimzade, S. A. Khalilov), Armenian (P. S. Bediryan, Ye. U. Gevorkyan, A. A. Murvalyan), A. M. Sukiasyan), Bashkir (Z.G. Uraksin), Belarusian (A.S. Aksamitov, A.M. Bazlenko, F.M. Yankovsky), Georgian (M.K. Andronikashvili, A.L. Oniani, A.A. Takaishvili), Kabardin (Kabardin-Circassian A.G. Emuzov, B.M. Kardanov), Kazakh (S.K. Kenesbaev, R. Sarsembaev, S.Tulekova), karakalpak (E. Berdimuradov, S.T. Nauruzbaeva, Kerimjonova, Dj. Osmonova, D. Shukurov, A. Sapparbaev, A. Nazarov), Kurdish (Yu. .Yu. Avaliani, M.H. Khamoyan), Latvian (E.K. Kagayne, E. Kokare, L. Ya.Orlovskaya), Lezgin (A.G. Gyulmagomedov), Lithuanian (B. Kalinauskas, Ya. Lipskene), Mari (F.T. Gracheva, E.S. Yakimova), Moldovan (R.S. Shirmankina), Ossetian (M.I. Isaev, I.A. Khugaev), Tajik (Kh. Majidov, I.Hasanov, S.V.Khushenova, N.Juraev), tatar (G.Kh.Akhatov, G.Kh.Axunzyanov, K.S.Sabirov), turkmen (A.Abdurahmonova, K.Babaev, G.Achilova, O.Nazarov, A. .Annamamedov), turkish (R.R.Yusipova, L.N.Dolganov), Uighur (A.T. Kaydarov, Ch.G. Sayfullin, O. Jamaldinov), Ukrainian (N.A. Moskalenko, L.G. Skripnik, G.M. Udovnichenko), Persian (Yu.A.Rubinchik), Chuvash (Yu.F.Efimov, M.F.Chernov), Estonian (F.Vakk, A.A.Krikmann) languages, significant works have been published. In particular, Ashurova D. U and Galiyeva M. R “Cultural linguistics”, Mamontov A.S. “Language and culture: a comparative aspect of the study” A.Nurmonov's "Linguoculturological direction in the Uzbek language", N.Mahmudov's "In search of perfect research ways of language", G.Mahkamova's “Culture matters”, Azizova's articles “Linguoculturological aspect of phraseological units as an object of translation”, “National-cultural specificity of English and Uzbek phraseological units in teaching”, “The system of exercises in teaching translation of english phraseological units from english into uzbek language”, Sayidrahimova's articles "Some remarks on the scientific basis of linguoculturology", "Components of linguoculturology", D.Khudoyberganova's "Anthropocentric study of the text" articles and monographs can be marked as a fact of the researches that are being carried out in the field. According to all aforementioned researches' results in terms of comparing somatic idioms in two languages, we can classify them into three groups:

I. Full compliance.

This sub-group consists of phraseological units (PU), based on body part components in the two compared languages.

Go behind someone 's back –birovni orqasidan ish qilmoq;

Be two –faced –ikkiyuzlamachi;

Stick your nose in –burnini tiqmoq;

On the tip of my tongue –tilini uchida turmoq;

II. Partial matching.

This includes the PU of the same lexical composition, but differ in the semantic and stylistic potential:

Up to your ears in something – ishi boshidan oshgan ;

Sweet tooth- shirin tomoq;

III. The lack of correspondences.

Further analysis of phraseological units in English and Uzbek languages reveal substantial differences in the benchmarks from speakers of these languages. These differences are determined by the differences of the two cultures (linked with the realities of life characteristic of the English and Uzbek features of natural conditions and traditions of these peoples). These words are the realities, rather, associates of the word stimuli associative reactions which are not bearers of the national characteristics of a particular language because of their extra-linguistic features! These words of reality and the English language: *kick the bucket*. The literal meaning of this phrase does not suggest its figurative meaning *to die*. The origin of the idiom related to the religious event. *Worth a Jew's eye*- very valuable. This idiom has also historical origin that belongs to the Jews.

In the Uzbek language: “*ko`zining paxtasi chiqdi*”, “*ko`zi yorimoq*”, “*ko`zini moshdek ochmoq*”(Rahmatullayev, 1978). These idioms has been recognized in scientific literature as "non-equivalent lexis". It shows us we can develop students' knowledge through culture of two countries.

Main body

Good teachers should be able to relate the teaching materials to daily usage or practical examples. By providing appropriate applications, students will be able to remember them better and longer. We need to turn to the types of activities foreign language teachers use in a classroom. The whole range of techniques varies from comprehension exercises to creative writing tasks. The most general examples available to students of various levels are the following: Watching a suggested film cuts and writing down an idiom/idioms used. This activity, though very common, enables the listeners both to memorize the idiom and to enjoy the process of watching a funny and entertaining film cuts. There are plenty of ways of making the teaching process more interesting and affective by using phraseological units. The teacher may explain the idiom first and then may give the definition orally and ask the students to make up examples one by one. The next way may be like this: the teacher may tell the idiom and give just the example and the students should give the definition it is that what today's up- to- date interactive methods requires us to accomplish. Another one is the students will be arranged into small groups and are supposed to make up short stories according to the phraseological units given by their teacher for example, *give the cold shoulder* but should not tell the idiom which is supposed to be used in the story. The next group should find the name of the phraseological units. The next activity goes on like following: the teacher hands in the written task which has multiple choice tests belonging to the idioms or phraseological units that should be learned. As a consequence, by choosing appropriate materials

for implementing different activities in teaching phraseological units are considerable too important. Teaching materials, part of the five needed components of language instruction (students, a teacher, materials, teaching methods, and evaluation), is a general term to refer to „anything which is used by teachers or learners to facilitate the learning of a language“ (Tomlinson, 1998). Teaching materials are of great importance for their guidance in any instructional circumstance. Brown (1995:139) mentions that they provide a detailed description of teaching techniques, methods and the tasks designed for a learner’s classroom activities. There are many types of teaching materials including paper-based (textbooks), electronic (corpus, computer software), and audio-visual (video, television programs, audio tapes, visual aids). They are important for the learning of language phraseology and may lead to success or failure to reach the competence aims. As the result of methodical interpretation of visual aids and other form of activities are developed considering specific goals in mind, linguistic and culture oriented peculiarities of the film and its thematic range. The exercises are directed at removing language difficulties, understanding the content of the episode for viewing, disclosure and discussion of the film, explanation of the realities of other cultures. These tasks can be divided into three groups: pre-viewing activities, first viewing activities and comprehension activities (Wu, Su-Yueh, 2008). It helps to facilitate the understanding of language units under study, to use analytical skills of students as much as possible, to mobilize their intimal resources, to increase the interest to the lessons. In such way it is facilitated the comprehension of foreign language speech and the construction of the statements, as the picture in the frame recreates the situation of communication and the student tries to "see", "to read" situational cues and use them as if a prepared or unprepared statement English language phraseological units using audio-visual aids involves the equipment of methodological apparatus of the pedagogical system in question, the didactic interpretation of authentic viewing episodes as well as the programming of certain training actions, aimed at mastering phraseological units with components body parts by the learners, the development of necessary speaking skills, the formation of a foreign language competence. For all that we should consider not only the native language of students, but the specifics of national culture, educational traditions, which aim to increase the effectiveness of linguoeducational process. Since learning a foreign language requires both students and teachers to be creative, the latter should be motivated to apply various modern techniques of teaching English phraseology with component expressing body parts (including idioms). While watching authentic video materials, memorizing and playing back or learning idioms which can be organizing through various vocabulary-based activities with textbooks is useful and also taking into consideration that although listening and pronouncing are separate skills, the majority of language skills are not and should not be taught separately. Speaking activities, discussion or pair-work are challenging and hugely motivating, and a focus on phraseology makes the language natural and authentic.

All in all, the above-mentioned activities help to overcome some linguistic challenges caused by studying idiomatic expressions and give a perfect example of how culture infuses a language.

Unlike the exercises listed above, we took into account that students are active in the field of technology and the Internet. We decided to move away from traditional activities and exercises and use a modern platform. The platform “QUIZZIZ” is a new way of applying exercises for checking students’ comprehension. It offers multiple tools to make a classroom fun, engaging, and interactive! As a teacher, we can create gamified Quizzes and Lessons, conduct formative

assessments, host live activities or assign them as homework, tap into detailed performance reports, and so much more! “QUIZZIZ” has a number of features that enable us to save time while we support learners on their path to mastery. It can be used to create personalized learning experiences. Teachers can create quizzes that are tailored to the specific needs of their students. Additionally, it can be used to assess student learning. Teachers can track student progress and identify areas where additional support is needed. The platform is a powerful educational platform that is revolutionizing learning. As it continues to grow and evolve, it is sure to have a major impact on education in the years to come.

Our research has analyzed 7 distinct types of questions integrated within the platform. They are:

- Drag and drop (figure1)
- Reorder in ascending order (figure2)
- Clarify the options into the corresponding groups (fig3)
- Answer questions based on below comprehension (fig4)
- Match the following (fig5)
- Fill in the blank (fig6)
- Open question: justify your answer with an explanation (fig7)

Figure1

Figure2

Figure3

Figure4

Figure5

Figure6

Figure7

This innovative technology serves as a valuable tool in capturing student engagement and facilitating effective learning. Given the digitally savvy nature of today's youth, such tools are instrumental in enhancing educational outcomes.

Conclusion

The current paper has dealt with two primary issues: describing semantic features of English and Uzbek idioms containing human-body parts and then working out the similarities and differences between English and Uzbek idioms containing human body parts used in different sources. The chosen materials for practicing were taken from films.

In short, it is expected that readers of this paper will, to some extent, draw out useful experience for themselves to enrich their idiom vocabulary and facilitate their translation competences. As cultural barriers among languages are still in existence, the teachers should equip themselves with suitable and effective strategies for teaching idioms in general and somatic idioms in particular from English into Uzbek. The Lingua-cultural approach helps them to do it successfully. Because it broadens cultural awareness of students; they learn not only language but the traditions and customs of the English people, they become more tolerant of other cultures, they start to respect other people's beliefs through the prism of Uzbek lingua-cultural heritage.

Moreover, the system of exercises was utilized while teaching and its modern formation “QUIZZIZ” can be intriguing to readers and teachers in terms of using them for different purposes in the lesson.

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